

Coherence, Distance and Error: Understanding Coded Demodulation in PB-ToF Imaging

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Abstract—One of the main objectives in coded Time-of-Flight is to precisely determine the position of the recovered target(s) with very few measurements or, in other words, to increase the resolution of the sensing system at high frame rates. In this scenario, we may cope with highly-coherent sensing matrices, i. e., there exist several columns very similar to each other. This may yield severe errors during the depth's retrieval. In this paper, we show that the foreseen potential (probable) mismatches in the support estimation are related to the distance between the most cross-correlated columns over the sensing matrix, and propose a, to our knowledge, new metric which allows for estimating the average (absolute) recovery error. The metric is given by the mean absolute distance between each column and the most cross-correlated columns over the sensing matrix. We numerically evaluate various state-of-the-art demodulation schemes, and demonstrate that our metric reliably provides an estimation of their recovery performance, and complements other metrics traditionally used in Computational Sensing.

Index Terms—Coded demodulation, Coherence, Compressive Sensing, Recoverability, Time-of-Flight

I. INTRODUCTION

The ultimate objective of any 3D imaging system is to provide a reliable representation of the scene being observed to, eventually, allow for safer and more cost-efficient actions and decisions to the final user. In this respect, Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras and, specially, the ones built upon amplitude-modulated light signals have become a fruitful niche of investigation in the last decades. The introduction of Compressed Sensing (CS) has definitely allowed for shorter acquisition times and storage needs, but also introduced some challenges during the recovery. In recent years, much attention has been paid to correct the errors derived from the scene being observed, i. e., the presence of translucent objects or multiple light paths at the vicinity of corners. In addition, various research groups [1], [2] designed close-to-optimal demodulation schemes aiming to minimize the acquisition time, increase the range, and push the resolution bounds further. The use of an appropriate metric to confidently determine the foreseen estimation error derived from the sensing model is an essential task that so far has relied on the oracle-given Cramer-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) [3]. We propose an original metric to a priori estimate the sensor reconstruction accuracy. In

addition, we evaluate several practical aspects which may have an impact on the performance during operation.

II. FUNDAMENTALS AND THEORETICAL DESCRIPTION

A. Compressive Sensing based Time-of-Flight

In indirect Pulse-based (PB) ToF cameras [4], [5] based on coded demodulation schemes, the distance to the target(s) (or depth) is estimated from m samples $[y_i]_{i=1}^m$ resulting from the correlation of m correlation functions $\vec{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ produced in the camera and repeated at a frequency f_r during the exposure time t_{exp} and the response function of the scene (1), being $\{\Gamma[k], \tau[k]\}_{k=0}^{s-1}$ the delays and reflectivities introduced by s return light paths arriving at the pixel (2).

$$\vec{x} = \left[\sum_{k=0}^{s-1} \Gamma[k] \delta(t_j - \tau[k]) \right]_{j=1}^n \quad (1)$$

Each correlation function $[\vec{a}_i]_{i=1}^m$ can be represented as the result of the convolution of an ideally (0,1)-binary pixel control signal $[\vec{a}_{0,i}]_{i=1}^m$ and a cross-correlation function \vec{p} , i. e., $\vec{a}_i = \vec{a}_{0,i} * \vec{p}$ [6], [7], which models the entire modulation-demodulation sequence, derives from the convolution of the emitted light pulse \vec{r} and the response function of the system $\vec{\eta}$, i. e., $\vec{p} = \vec{r} * \vec{\eta}$, and can be expressed as a Gaussian filter of Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) $\sim \mathcal{O}(\text{ns})$. Each of the n_0 elements of $\vec{a}_{0,i}$ is divided in n_s sub-steps, prior to the convolution with \vec{p} , which allows for depth super-resolution.

$$y_i = \vec{a}_i \cdot \vec{x} + \varepsilon_i = (\vec{a}_{0,i} * \vec{p}) \cdot \vec{x} + \varepsilon_i, \text{ with } 1 \leq i \leq m \quad (2)$$

Since $m \ll n$, being $n = n_0 \times n_s$, (2) is under-determined, being $\vec{\varepsilon}$ the sensor readout noise. However, the inverse problem translates into a constrained ℓ_0 -minimization problem (3) when accounting for the sparsity of \vec{x} in the time (or depth) domain, i. e., the fact that \vec{x} only contains a small number of non-zero entries ($s \ll n$).

$$\hat{\vec{x}} = \arg \min_{\vec{x}} \|\vec{x}\|_0, \quad \text{subject to: } \vec{y} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \vec{x} + \vec{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

This ℓ_0 -norm minimization problem is non-convex and \mathcal{NP} -hard to solve. To allow for a fast computation, several approaches have been explored. Some of them were built upon classical greedy algorithms [8], on the minimization of the ℓ_1 -norm, or based on the implementation of a thresholding operator followed by a partial re-projection of the residual.

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Fig. 1. **First row:** Correlation function generated via gradient-Combinatorial for $f_m = 448$ MHz and $f_r = 7$ MHz, and an emitted light pulse characterized by $0.5 \text{ ns} \leq \text{FWHM} \leq 5 \text{ ns}$. **Second row:** Experimental evaluation and numerical simulation of the correlation function generated via gradient-Combinatorial for $f_m = 448$ MHz and $f_r = 3.5$ MHz, and an emitted light pulse of $\text{FWHM} = 1.45 \text{ ns}$ (experimental) corresponding to a calibrated Gaussian filter of $\text{FWHM} = 2 \text{ ns}$ in our numerical simulation.

Fig. 2. Sensing matrices and corresponding Gram matrices, generated via random (0,1)-binary codes, Scrambled Hadamard Ensembles (SHEs) plus (0,1)-rescaling, gradient-Combinatorial, and the ones based on Gray and Hamiltonian codes for various emitted light pulse widths characterized by $\text{FWHM} = 0.5 \text{ ns}, 1 \text{ ns}, \text{ and } 5 \text{ ns}$.

B. Demodulation Schemes and Sensing Matrices.

Good sensing matrices \mathbf{A} yield shorter acquisition times and reduce the computational cost associated to the scene reconstruction. In this respect, Lopez Paredes *et al.* [1] proposed a close-to-optimal demodulation scheme coined gradient-Combinatorial, built upon Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) codes, which employs a combinatorial approach plus a correlation evaluation step to establish a maximally

incoherent arrangement of \mathbf{A} . This step, effectively, avoids the self-intersection of the coding curves. Also, Gupta *et al.* [9] and Gutierrez-Barragan *et al.* [10] designed an original family of coding functions based on Hamiltonian codes on the hypercube graph. As shown in Fig. 2, we evaluate both approaches together with other non-deterministic methodologies [11], [12] to estimate the foreseen mismatches in the support estimation derived from the sensing model.

C. Impact of the Instrument Response and Code Length.

As illustrated in the first row of Fig. 1, the behaviour of $[\vec{a}_i]_{i=1}^m$ is significantly dependant on the Instrument Response Function (IRF) and, therefore, on the duration of the emitted light pulse. As described in Section II-A, we can exploit the non-negligible duration of the emitted light signal to discretize $a_{0,i}^j$ in n_s steps, yielding a grid much finer than the one established by the original length of the (0,1)-binary codes. However, for a given code trigger frequency (f_m), very short light pulses lead to identical columns close to each other at the centre of each element of the (0,1)-binary code and, thus, compromise the resolution enhancement. On the other hand, excessively long pulses translate to smoother transitions from one element to another of \vec{a}_i , differences in the modulation capacity (lower and uneven peak voltages over \vec{a}_i), and an eventual deterioration of the sparse nature of \mathbf{A} . From the point of view of the hardware implementation, very short pulses may yield an unstable and unreliable performance of the illumination system (usually for FWHM ≤ 1 ns), whilst, wider and, thus, more-energetic pulses yield higher power requirements. Moreover, we present in the second row of Fig. 1 an experimental characterization of the demodulation functions with our laboratory-designed ToF camera¹, together with the one numerically simulated using the same (0,1)-binary code, and shows the very good agreement between simulated and measured responses, which proves the feasibility of actually implementing our coded demodulation scheme with a ToF camera.

III. PROPOSED PERFORMANCE METRIC

For ToF cameras aiming to approach real-time operation, m shall be minimized due to the fact that, as any imaging system, ToF sensors require an exposure time $t_{\text{exp}} \sim \mathcal{O}(\text{ms})$ to gather enough light. In addition, the increase of the non-ambiguous range r_{max} , i.e., of n_0 , and the enhancement of the depth resolution, given by the fine discretization of the time domain, lead to \mathbf{A} characterized by $m \ll n$ and, thus, coherence $\mu \rightarrow 1$ (4). In this scenario, the correct identification of the signal support may not be guaranteed [8]. However, the magnitude of the depth estimation error may substantially differ from one sensing matrix to another, even if both attain the same μ .

$$\mu = \max \left(\frac{|\langle \vec{a}^j, \vec{a}^k \rangle|}{\|\vec{a}^j\|_2 \|\vec{a}^k\|_2} \right) \text{ with } j \neq k \quad (4)$$

Other metrics, such as the root mean square (RMS) of the column cross-correlations or the Babel Function (cumulative or total coherence), may be useful to provide guarantees for the recoverability of the target's depth. The Babel Function $\mu_1(p)$ [8] provides a better understanding about how $[\vec{a}^j]_{j=1}^n$ are similar to each other. It is given by the maximum total coherence between a fixed column \vec{a}^j which ranges over the

¹In our experimental setup, the pulse width measured is FWHM = 1.45 ns, whilst the calibrated Gaussian filter to match the pixel response in our numerical simulation is FWHM = 2 ns.

Fig. 3. Foreseen error during the estimation of signal support via Gram matrix for a sensing matrix generated upon random (0,1)-binary codes.

columns indexed by $\Omega \setminus \Lambda$ and any set of other columns \mathbf{A}_Λ with $|\Lambda| = p$ (5). It is a characteristic of quasi-incoherent dictionaries that $\mu_1(p)$ grows slowly with p [8].

$$\mu_1(p) = \max_{|\Lambda|=p} \left(\max_{\vec{a}^j} \left(\sum_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \frac{|\langle \vec{a}^j, \vec{a}^\lambda \rangle|}{\|\vec{a}^j\|_2 \|\vec{a}^\lambda\|_2} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

Still $\mu_1(p)$ does not directly translate into a prediction of the depth estimation error in the noisy case. We present a, to our knowledge, original metric $\delta_G^j = \delta_G^j(\varepsilon_0)$, being the threshold² $\varepsilon_0 \rightarrow 1$, that helps us to predict the error due to erroneous estimation of the signal support. In this respect, the Gram matrix \mathbf{G} (of \mathbf{A} normalized by columns) contains insightful information about how the columns of the sensing matrix are related to each other. We make use of \mathbf{G} , such that $g_j^k = \frac{|\langle \vec{a}^j, \vec{a}^k \rangle|}{\|\vec{a}^j\|_2 \|\vec{a}^k\|_2}$ with $1 \leq j \leq n$ and $1 \leq k \leq n$, and define the set $\{\Phi_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\Gamma = \{\gamma_j\}_{j=1}^n$ being $\gamma_j := \{j\}$ (6).

$$\Phi_j = \text{clos}_{\varepsilon_0, 1}(\gamma_j) = \{k \in \Gamma \mid k \neq j, g_j^k \geq \varepsilon_0\} \quad (6)$$

Then, we calculate δ_G^j as the mean absolute distance of the identified column indices in Φ_j (6) with respect to j (7). As shown in Fig. 3, we may fall into two different scenarios:

- $\delta_G^j \gg n_s$, which may lead to large depth estimation errors, are the result of either identical $[\vec{a}_0]_{j=1}^{n_0}$ or the coincident rising and falling edges due to non-instantaneous transition times from one element to another of the code yielding identical columns in \mathbf{A} [1]. This can be observed in the cross-correlation factors for $\vec{a}^{j=16}$ on the top right sub-plot of Fig. 3.
- $\delta_G^j \approx n_s$, which may lead to low depth estimation errors, derives from the characterization of $[\vec{a}_i]_{i=1}^m$ in a grid with $n_s > n$, as illustrated on the bottom right sub-plot of Fig. 3 for the cross-correlation factors for $\vec{a}^{j=100}$.

$$\delta_G^j = \text{mean}_{\Phi_j}(|\phi_j^k - j|) \quad (7)$$

As a result of (7), we obtain the distribution $\Delta_G = [\delta_G^j]_{j=1}^n$ over the sensing matrix \mathbf{A} , being the mean value $\delta_{G,A} = \text{mean}(\Delta_G)$ representative of the inherent reconstruction error derived from \mathbf{A} for sparse vectors.

² $\varepsilon_0 := \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2}$ from [13].

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A. Preliminary Considerations

We present the typical design parameters of our CS-based ToF camera [4] in Table I in semi-continuous rotation. We make use of the depth maps and transient profiles from the state-of-the-art dataset [14] to validate the proposed approach. We select the maximum peak of each transient profile and the corresponding intensity, multiplied by $\iota = 10^4$ to adjust it to the expected measurement levels during operation, as our Ground Truth (GT). To allow for a fair comparison of the methodologies employing different m , we adjust the intensity of \vec{x} to ensure equal total t_{exp} . Then, the measurements are corrupted, accounting for the sensor readout noise, by adding normally distributed random noise.

Property	Symbol	Value
Clock trigger frequency	f_m	448 MHz
Repetition frequency	f_r	7 MHz
Non-ambiguous range	r_{max}	21.4 m
Grid size (depth resolution)	Δr	0.056 m
Number of sub-steps	n_s	6
Number of measurements	m	5 – 10
Emitted light pulse width	FWHM	0.5 ns – 5 ns

TABLE I

TYPICAL OPERATIONAL PARAMETERS OF OUR CS-BASED TOF CAMERA.

B. Evaluation of Different Demodulation Schemes

We find that \mathbf{A} built via gradient-Combinatorial presents the lowest $\mu_1(p)$ for all cases over the range studied, and that the obtained $\delta_{G,A}$ is similar in Gray-based and gradient-Combinatorial methodologies with $\delta_{G,A} < n_s$ over the studied range. In addition, we find that Gray-based and gradient-Combinatorial schemes present the highest probability of reaching $\delta_G^j < n_s$ being $\{j\}_{j=1}^n$ the indices of the columns of \mathbf{A} . Another interesting result is the relevant reduction of $\delta_{G,A}$ with FWHM until reaching a local minimum followed by a smooth increase in all the construction methodologies. This reduction, especially relevant for Hamiltonian-based codes, yields a subsequent reduction of depth estimation error. In addition, Fig.6 presents the recovered depth maps for two scenes [14] evaluated via OMP. Finally, Table II and Table III show the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) along with $\delta_{G,A}$ and the probability of reaching super-resolution for this particular realization of the scenes.

C. Other Practical Aspects: Impact of the Exposure time.

An increase of m for a given t_{exp} budget yields a lower intensity perceived by the pixel, a higher sensitivity to noise and, subsequently, a larger depth estimation error. We choose \mathbf{A} generated via gradient-Combinatorial [1] with $n_{\text{deg}} = 3$ non-zero elements per column, and fix the total t_{exp} for $m = 10$. We present the depth estimation errors in terms of RMSE of bathroom and bedroom from [14] in Fig. 7 for various noise levels, and an emitted light pulse of FWHM = 1 ns.

Fig. 4. Total coherence ($\mu_1(p)$ and $\frac{\mu_1(p)}{p}$) for sensing matrices generated via various methodologies considering $f_r = 7$ MHz and $f_m = 448$ MHz.

Fig. 5. Mean distance to highly-correlated columns $\delta_{G,A}(\epsilon_0)$ and probability of reaching super-resolution, i. e., $\delta_G^j(\epsilon_0) \leq n_s$ with $\epsilon_0 \geq 0.9$ for sensing matrices generated via various methodologies considering $f_r = 7$ MHz and $f_m = 448$ MHz.

Fig. 6. Depth maps of scenes bathroom (top) and bedroom (bottom) obtained via OMP with additive random noise of std.dev. = 0.1 and FWHM ≤ 5 ns.

FWHM [ns]	$\delta_{G,A} (0.99)$ [col.]			$P(\delta_{G,A} (0.99) < n_s)$ [-]			SSIM [-]			MAE [mm]			RMSE [mm]		
	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0
random	4.222	4.056	1.733	0.971	0.972	0.998	0.644	0.999	1.000	25.6	0.3	0.2	49.9	5.8	3.5
(0,1)-SHE	2.885	2.649	2.629	0.995	0.995	0.990	0.639	0.999	1.000	26.5	0.3	0.1	54.0	5.1	2.5
gComb	2.006	1.437	1.271	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.632	0.998	1.000	27.8	0.4	0.2	52.7	5.6	3.8
Gray m=6	2.075	1.923	1.892	0.994	0.994	1.000	0.651	0.999	1.000	24.7	0.3	0.2	47.7	4.6	2.9
Ham. m=5	14.039	12.446	2.436	0.609	0.642	0.934	0.150	0.376	1.000	287.5	154.6	≤ 0.1	383.0	237.2	1.8

TABLE II

STRUCTURAL SIMILARITY INDEX (SSIM), MEAN ABSOLUTE ERROR (MAE), AND ROOT MEAN SQUARE ERROR (RMSE) CORRESPONDING TO THE DEPTH MAPS OF scene₁ : BATHROOM (FIG. IV-B) RECOVERED VIA OMP FOR ADDITIVE RANDOM NOISE OF std. dev. = 0.1.

FWHM [ns]	$\delta_{G,A} (0.99)$ [col.]			$P(\delta_{G,A} (0.99) < n_s)$ [-]			SSIM [-]			MAE [mm]			RMSE [mm]		
	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0	0.5	1.0	5.0
random	4.222	4.056	1.733	0.971	0.972	0.998	0.567	0.890	0.945	124.4	30.9	15.2	568.2	320.0	295.5
(0,1)-SHE	2.885	2.649	2.629	0.995	0.995	0.990	0.645	0.954	0.956	47.0	8.1	7.9	156.6	148.3	114.7
gComb	2.006	1.437	1.271	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.650	0.963	0.959	46.1	6.1	9.0	78.9	87.8	170.8
Gray m=6	2.075	1.923	1.892	0.994	0.994	1.000	0.672	0.969	0.978	41.9	5.0	4.1	71.2	20.4	17.9
Ham. m=5	14.039	12.446	2.436	0.609	0.642	0.934	0.187	0.381	0.968	274.7	154.6	5.9	376.8	249.7	25.8

TABLE III

STRUCTURAL SIMILARITY INDEX (SSIM), MEAN ABSOLUTE ERROR (MAE), AND ROOT MEAN SQUARE ERROR (RMSE) CORRESPONDING TO THE DEPTH MAPS OF scene₂ : BEDROOM (FIG. IV-B) RECOVERED VIA OMP FOR ADDITIVE RANDOM NOISE OF std. dev. = 0.1.

FWHM	rand.	SHE	GComb	Gray	Ham.
0.5 ns	0.557	0.633	0.405	0.554	0.525
1.0 ns	0.585	0.662	0.424	0.560	0.529
2.0 ns	0.652	0.725	0.476	0.576	0.536
5.0 ns	0.800	0.850	0.637	0.628	0.560

TABLE IV

RMS-VALUE OF THE COLUMN CROSS-CORRELATION OVER SENSING MATRICES GENERATED VIA VARIOUS METHODOLOGIES, WITH $f_r = 7$ MHz AND $f_m = 448$ MHz.

Fig. 7. Depth estimation error obtained for the scenes bathroom (left) and bedroom (right) via OMP with $f_m = 448$ MHz, $f_r = 7$ MHz, and sensing matrices generated via gradient-Combinatorial with FWHM = 1 ns.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTIVE WORK

In this paper, we shed light on the link between quality of the sensing scheme and reconstruction error. We have proposed a practical methodology to preliminary estimate the depth estimation error and the probability of super-resolution for a given coding scheme, and evaluated the sensing matrices generated via various state-of-the-art methodologies [1], [2], [10], and traditional approaches. Prospective work includes the evaluation of our approach with real measurements.

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